

THE ASSESSMENT OF PSYCHOLOGICAL WELL-BEING AMONG UNIVERSITY STUDENTS CONCERNING GENDER

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Abstract

The psychological well-being of university students is a public health issue. They face multiple challenges during their academic life and to perform efficiently in the academic domain they are required to deal with these challenges in an effective way. Certain demographic characteristics are associated with the phenomena of psychological wellbeing. This study is aimed to compare the scales of psychological well-being with concern to gender among university students of Karachi. The cross-sectional analytical study design was adopted and a sample of 180 (90 males and 90 females) undergraduate students within the age bracket of 18 to 30 years from different departments of public and private universities in Karachi participated. The scales of psychological well-being by Ryff were administered to participants and data was gathered through the survey method. Statistical analysis was done by applying a t-test to identify the difference between both groups. Findings revealed significant gender differences ($p < .05$). Female participants scored significantly higher on all domains of psychological wellbeing. Influencing factors, recommendations, and implications of the study are further discussed.

INTRODUCTION

In modern Psychology, the notion of well-being is a well-acknowledged and extensively researched topic. Deci and Ryan (2008) described wellbeing as “optimal psychological experience and functioning”. However, the philosophical roots of this simple topic are controversial and complex (Kashdan, Biswas-Diener, & King, 2008). The philosophical foundation of wellbeing is based on two concepts: hedonia and eudaimonia. Hedonia is defined as pleasure or hedonic enjoyment and eudaimonia is concerned with fulfilling one’s inner potential (Deci & Ryan, 2008). Empirical pieces of evidence (Kashdan, Biswas-Diener, & King, 2008; Kraut, 1979) have reported the correlation between these two concepts; however, from the conceptual point of view they are

different (Kashdan, Biswas-Diener, & King, 2008).

The origin of psychological wellbeing is formulated on the assumption of “eudaimonia” (Waterman, 1993). That is concerned with the meaning of life, virtue, and fully functioning person or self-actualization as suggested by Maslow (1970). Eudaimonic assumption describes wellbeing as an ongoing process in which a person realizes his or her “inner inherent potentials” (Ryff C. , 2017). Waterman (1990) described eudaimonia as the concept of self-expressiveness and this self-expressiveness can be attained through the activities that increase or facilitate one’s inner true potential. He further elaborated that self-expressiveness is the combination of three different psychological

concepts i.e. intrinsic motivation, flow, and self-actualization. Concerning its functionality, it has the buffering effect and works as a protective factor to counter psychological distress and mental illness (Ryff C. , 2017).

Ryff (1989) recognized the need to specify the essential characteristics of psychological wellbeing. She targeted the various theories or domains by Allport (1961), Buhler (1935), Erikson (1959), Frankl (1992), Jahuda (1958), Jung (1933), Maslow (1970), Neugarten (1968), Rogers (1962) of positive human psychological functioning and integrated them into a model of psychological wellbeing based on six-dimension namely; Autonomy, Environmental mastery, Positive relations with others, Purpose in life, Personal growth and Self-acceptance. "Self-acceptance" is a core feature of optimal psychological wellbeing and is concerned with accepting one's strengths and weaknesses. The domain of "Positive relationships with others" is associated with making positive, warm, and trusting relationships with the members of society. People with this quality show unconditioned love and empathy toward humanity. The domain of "Autonomy" is focused on self-determined human behavior that is completely regulated by self. All decisions of life are based on independent decision-making rather than getting forced by societal pressure. The characteristic of "Environmental mastery" integrates the element of active participation in society and the ability to manipulate the environment according to one's set of mind or strengths. Hence, people with this ability tend to actively participate in society and get rejoiced by availing themselves of all opportunities of life. The domain of "Purpose in life" is associated with goal-directed behaviors in life. They consistently get the feeling that their existence in the world is meaningful. That's why their attitude toward life is self-directed and goal-oriented. And the last domain, "Personal growth" is concerned with progressive development and advancement in one's life. People with this quality are open to experiencing and exploring the world to learn from different experiences (Ryff C. D., 1989).

The concern of mental health among university students is a public health issue. Various studies have identified students as a highly vulnerable group of society to psychological problems or illnesses such as anxiety, depression, relational problems, and many others. From the developmental point of view, adulthood followed by entering university is a transitional period. During this period of developmental transition, students get exposed to multiple stressors or difficulties, for example, decision making related to their career, adjustment issue, fulfilling university demands related to academic performance, making and maintaining interpersonal relationships with classmates and teachers (Cleary, Walter, & Jackson, 2010; Hamaideh, 2009). Overall, these difficulties or stressors make university students more prone to physical, mental, and cognitive (attention and concentration-related issues) risk factors (Shankar & Park, 2016).

There is an abundance of research reflecting university students at the increased level of mental distress and recognized risk factors include financial issues, relational problems, isolation, lack of social support, declined functioning in academic performance, history of psychological problems in the family, and having gender of female (Cleary, Walter, & Jackson, 2010; Dachew, Bisetegn, & Gebremariam, 2015; Hamaideh, 2009; Hersi, Tesfay, Gesesew, Krahl, Ereg, & Tesfaye, 2017).

In the field of positive psychology research the study and evaluation of psychological well-being by considering gender differences is a very important factor. This assessment enables students to get self-realization and pursue their full potential (Sagone & Caroli, 2014). Research conducted on psychological wellbeing in different regions of the globe report significant gender difference. Ryff (2017) also identified gender as a significant correlate of psychological wellbeing. The empirical shreds of evidence from her research work indicate the domains of positive relations with others and personal growth as the significant correlates of psychological wellbeing among females. These findings were also supported by Matud and colleagues (2019).

Chraifa and Dumitru (2015) further verified that apart from these two domains of psychological wellbeing, females have better level of self-acceptance as compared to males. Nilsson et al. (2010), found better psychological well-being among males in comparison to females. Another research found males to be high scorers in the domain of “autonomy” and “self-acceptance” (Chraif & Dumitru, 2015),

Overall, it can be concluded that research (Perez, 2012; Siddiqui, 2015; Nilsson, Leppert, Simonsson, & Starrin, 2010) related to psychological wellbeing yields different as well as contradictory findings to each other. However, this variation confirms the idea that psychological well-being is a culturally influenced phenomenon. Secondly, there is a need to identify the factors that contribute to the difference in the psychological well-being of males and females in a respective culture. This study is also expected to extend the local evidence where previous work provides very limited shreds of evidence on this subject. These are the factors that highlight the rationale for conducting this research. So the fundamental objective of this study is to assess the psychological well-being of university students in their context (Karachi). And, it was hypothesized that there would be significant divergence between the psychological well-being of students concerning gender.

Methodology

Sample

This study was conducted on 180 undergraduate students within the age bracket of 18 to 30 years (Mean age= 22.13years). The sample was divided into two broad categories 90 male and 90 female participants. The sample was extracted from various social sciences departments of the University of Karachi and Jinnah University for Women by using convenient sampling technique. Data was only collected from those students who consented for participation in research and have at least spent three or more months in university. All ethical protocols were followed throughout the process of data collection. The data for this study was gathered during the time frame of February 2018 to March 2018.

Measures

Scales of Psychological Well-Being

Ryff (1989) developed these scales based on 54 statements and six domains namely; autonomy, environmental mastery, purpose in life, self-acceptance, personal growth, and positive relations with others. Each domain is made up of 9 statements, in which the respondent is instructed to specify his/her feeling on a 6 point rating scale (ranging from 1= strongly disagree) to 6 = strongly agree). The standard presentation format of scales is mixed (one statement from each scale (i.e. autonomy, environmental mastery, personal growth, positive relations with others purpose in life and self-acceptance) successively into one questionnaire of 63 statements. These scales have well-established psychometric properties (Seifert, 2005). Standard scoring protocol of scales was followed to score items positively and reversed, 324 is the highest, and 54 is the lowest score that a person can receive on scales of psychological wellbeing. However, there is no cut-off score for determining low or high well-being. The high scores indicate a high self-rating in the respective domain.

Procedure

Data collection procedure in universities was initiated by getting the signed approval of concerned university authorities and data was exclusively collected from the social sciences departments of both universities. Visiting a particular university or department was planned as per the instructions of the concerned authority. All the fieldwork of this research was entirely done by the principal investigator. Participants were approached individually and before participation, the document of informed consent was provided to participant that was comprised of briefed introduction about the purpose of research and rights of confidentiality, anonymity, participation, and withdrawal from the research.

After taking their consent, a demographic form sheet and questionnaire were provided to participants to enter their responses. The filled questionnaires were received hand to hand after assuring their completion. After the complete

procedure of data collection the standard protocol of scoring was followed to interpret the numbers. Detailed demographic characteristics of participants are provided in Table I.

Data analysis

The data of this study was analyzed by using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS, Version 22). The demographic characteristics of participants were summarized by using descriptive statistics (i.e. frequency, percentage, mean and

standard deviation) as shown in Table I, were applied to get the estimation of demographic characteristics of participants (i.e. gender, age, year of education, family system, and university). The Independent sample t-test (Table II) was computed to evaluate the gender difference on the scales of psychological wellbeing. To identify the difference the considered significance level was $p < .05$.

Results

Table I

Demographic characteristics of the sample and mean score on Ryff's scales of psychological wellbeing

Variables	N (%)	Mean Score
Total No of participants	180	208.87 (24.27)
Gender		
Male	90 (50)	203.36 (24.29)
Female	90 (50)	214.39 (23.09)
Year of education		
13th years of education	44 (24.4)	210.68 (25.69)
14th years of education	38 (21.11)	202.71 (19.10)
15th years of education	60 (11.66)	207.72 (22.28)
16th years of education	38 (21.11)	214.76 (29.08)
Birth order		
First	50 (27.77)	206.44 (23.35)
Middle	70 (38.88)	210.64 (24.43)
Last	60 (11.66)	208.83 (25.04)
Type of Family		
Nuclear	154 (85.55)	208.47 (24.01)
Joint	26 (14.44)	211.23 (26.10)
University		
University of Karachi	136 (75.5%)	206.13 (224.44)
Jinnah University for women	44 (24.44%)	217.87 (21.90)

Table II

Domain analysis of psychological well-being scales concerning gender (N= 180)

Variables	Groups	n	M	SD	t	df	Sig.
Overall	Male	90	203.36	24.292	-3.123	178	.002*
Psychological well-being	Female	90	214.39	23.093			
Positive relations with others	Male	90	34.44	5.742	-1.553	178	.122
	Female	90	35.82	6.156			
Autonomy	Male	90	33.71	5.024	-.926	178	.356
	Female	90	34.42	5.272			
Environmental Mastery	Male	90	34.36	4.986	-1.99	178	.048*
	Female	90	35.83	4.963			
Personal Growth	Male	90	32.37	5.787	-2.588	178	.010*
	Female	90	34.48	5.137			
Purpose in life	Male	90	32.97	6.068	-3.49	178	.001*
	Female	90	37.77	5.844			
Self-Acceptance	Male	90	35.51	5.364	-2.66	178	.008*
	Female	90	37.77	5.970			

*p<.05

This table shows that overall female participants scored significantly high on the scales of the psychological well-being as compared to male participant. Significant (p<.05) gender difference is observed in the domains of “Environmental mastery”, “Personal growth”, Purpose in life and “self-acceptance”. Female participants showed

significantly raised scores on described above domains of psychological wellbeing in comparison to male participants. However, no gender difference was observed in the domains of “Positive relations with others” and “Autonomy” (p>.05).

Figure 1: This graph is showing the mean scores of participants in the different domains of psychological wellbeing. It is observed that female participants have raised level of psychological wellbeing as compared to male participants.

Discussion

The present study was aimed to assess psychological well-being among university students concerning gender. It was hypothesized that there would be significant divergence between the psychological well-being of students concerning gender. To conduct this study a sample of having homogenous characteristics was chosen such as the same age group and educational level. The statistical analysis supported the hypothesis and revealed significant gender differences in the scores of psychological well-being of participants. Moreover, this study finds female participants on the advantage for scoring significantly high in most of the domains of psychological wellbeing as compared to male participants (Figure 1).

In the field of health and wellbeing, gender is one of the important influencing factors. Both genders differ in characteristics, behavior, attitude, and norms according to their culture (Manandhar, Hawkes, Kent, Nosrati, & Magar, 2018). Present study findings are supported by various research and signify the gender difference on the scales of psychological wellbeing (Ahren & Ryff, 2006; Karasawa, et al., 2011; Ryff & Keyes, 1995). Besides, there are some other researches as well that support high scores of females in the various domains of psychological wellbeing (Garcia-Alandete, Lozano, Nohales, & Martinez, 2013; Lindfors, Berntsson, & Lundberg, 2006; Karasawa, et al., 2011).

Such as, a study conducted in Pakistan reported that females are more emotionally intelligent than males (Bibi, Saqlain, & Mussawar, 2016). Researchers argue that escalation in the positive emotions of females is due to the bio-psychosocial model. It is evident from neuro-biological research (Abbruzzese, Magnani, Robert, & Mancuso, 2019; Somerville, Fani, & McClure-Tone, 2011) that females relatively use their brains more for the expression and identification or recognition of emotions than males. The usage of Mirror neurons was found to be high among females. The function of Mirror neurons is related to the grasping and understanding of one's point of view from behavioral and emotional perspectives (Dowthwaite, 2018).

Some researchers support the idea that the prevalence of positive emotions such as openness, empathy, prosocial behavior, positive interpersonal relations, and reflection is likely to be high among females (Dowthwaite, 2018; Sun & Stewart, 2012). Apart from positive emotions, females are better at coping with stress and have a high level of perceived social support from their social circle, help-seeking behavior, and better communications skills (Dowthwaite, 2018; Nicholls, Polman, Levy, Taylor, & Cobley, 2007). Results of this study also disapprove of the phenomena of gender inequality among university students and indicate that females are the better performer in the domains of wellbeing. Unfortunately, the image of a woman is usually associated with passivity and powerlessness. That's why they are often considered vulnerable to physical and mental health issues. However, the main reason behind their lacking is gender inequality which makes them vulnerable to physical and mental health disturbances (Smyth & Sweetman, 2015).

According to recent research findings (Hays, 2018) females are better in deal with adverse situations and have more life expectancy (approximately 80 years) and a low mortality rate as compared to males. World Health Organization (WHO) (2020) also reports a high ratio of life expectancy among females; they tend to live 6 to 8 years more in comparison to males. That could be attributed to their health-promoting behaviors for example females are less likely to get engaged in risk taking behaviors, substance abuse, and acting out behavior or aggression (World Health Organization, 2020). Overall, these could be the argumentative factors that render females score high in various domains of psychological wellbeing.

Age could be another confounding factor in the present study results. Svence & Majors (2015) found age as a significant correlate of psychological well-being and its dimensions. They argue that eudaimonic wellbeing gets reduced with increased aging. However, cognitive and transcendence well-being elevate with age.

Decreased psychological well-being among male participants could be attributed to the increased

level of depression among male university students (Wenjuan, Siquing, & Xinqiao, 2020). WHO reports (World Health Organization, 2020), that 77% of suicide is committed by people from middle and low socio-economic countries among which 58% of suicide is attempted before the age of 50 years. Moreover, at the global level males are 2.3 times high in rate of suicide as compared to females. According to a local retrospective study (Shakeel, 2019) during the year 2010 to 2017, it was 22% of the university population committed suicide and the major identified reason was failure in exams, relational problems, negative attitude toward teachers, dissatisfaction with life, academic pressure, and poverty.

Conclusion

This study is a primitive step to promote positive education of university students and assess the psychological well-being of university students. That is one of the most important factors in promoting mental health and positive education. The scales of psychological well-being by Ryff were used as a measure of the study. Obtained results supported the hypothesis and found that psychological well-being varies with gender and females have a better level of psychological well-being than males. These findings do not adhere to the traditional role of females in our society and provide evidence of women's empowerment. However, further empirical shreds of evidence are required for conclusive findings and contributing factors. Overall, this study was conducted on a very small scale and does not identify the factors that could be attributed to diverse progress of psychological wellbeing among university students concerning gender.

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